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D1.1. Project Handbook

Strengthening the Research Capacity of Turkey in Innovative
Business Models for the Hospitality Sector

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ATU	: Atlantic Technological University
BEN	: Beneficiary
BUU	: Bursa Uludag University
CA	: Consortium Agreement
CM	: Communication Manager
COO	: Coordinator
DM	: Data Manager
DMP	: Data Management Plan
DoA	: Description of Action
EB	: Executive Board
EC	: European Commission
EM	: Exploitation Manager
FM	: Financial Manager
GA	: General Assembly
IPR	: Intellectual Property Rights
KoM	: Kick-off Meeting
M	: Month
OA	: Open Access
PC	: Project Coordinator
PCR	: Portal Continuous Reporting
PM	: Project Manager
PMB	: Project Management Board
ULE	: Universidad De Leon
WP	: Work Package
WPL	: Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the first deliverable (D1.1.Project Handbook) of the REMODEL project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101079203.

REMODEL Project Handbook Consists of General Information About:

- REMODEL's Aim, Work Packages, Deliverables, and Milestones
- REMODEL's Governance Structure, and The Roles and Responsibilities of Each Level of the Governance Structure
- Rules to be Followed to Maintain Effective Internal and External Communication
- Document Preparation and Sharing
- Report Preparation
- Data Management

The Project Handbook is a guideline that helps partners carry out their responsibilities effectively and is an important tool for coordination. REMODEL Project Handbook consists of general information about the project and information about project management structure, the way of internal and external communication, document preparation, time management, data management, and conflict resolution.

The document does not replace the DEL Grant Agreement and REMODEL Consortium agreement, however stands for a complementary to the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement (CA).

The Dissemination level of the Project handbook is "public". It is an important tool to provide information to our stakeholders about project activities and management procedures. In this respect, this deliverable also serves as a source that can be used by anyone who carries out or wants to carry out EU funded and/or national projects.

The REMODEL Handbook is a living document. The 1st version of the handbook was finalised on 27 February 2023, uploaded to the continuous reporting module and shared with stakeholders on Zenado and the REMODEL project website. In the following process, due to mandatory changes in the project staff, it became necessary to update the handbook. The 2nd version of the handbook includes the revisions that were made taking into account the changes in the Project staff and some minor revision in Table 5, 6 and 7.

1. INTRODUCTION

REMODEL is funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program (under Grant Agreement No 101079203); Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence action, at the area of twinning which aims to develop excellence in chosen research and innovation domain, increase visibility of the research institutions and universities, and upskill its staff.

The Project Handbook is a project management tool that contributes to planning and coordination. Thanks to the REMODEL Project Handbook the consortium members will carry out their day-to-day project activities effectively. Also, stakeholders will receive information about REMODEL project management approach and procedures. Therefore the Project Handbook is an important information source for both consortium members and REMODEL stakeholders.

In compatibility with the REMODEL Gantt chart, D1.1. Project Handbook is delivered by the end of the M02. The handbook has been revised in M17 to reflect the effects of the mandatory change in project personnel. Some minor revisions have also been made to Tables 5, 6 and 7.

2. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT REMODEL

2.1. REMODEL Context and Objectives

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the worldwide economy and way of living. Its consequences have challenged the regular way of doing business, highlighting the vulnerabilities of the global economy under the current delocalization of production, and severe dependence on the movement of goods and people. One of the main sectors affected worldwide is tourism and hospitality.

The impact of COVID 19 e.g. restrictions imposed on travelers, inhabitants and businesses, the implementation of lock-down measures to prevent contagion and contain COVID-19 virus spread, has severely affected the day to day business operations of the SMEs in the hospitality sector, which is particularly severe for sectors in which human contact and social interaction are unavoidable.

Given the importance of the hospitality sector for Turkey, measures to mitigate COVID-19 socio-economic impacts on livelihoods need to be put in place urgently in order to improve competitiveness and build resilience against the impact the pandemic. This will require how the business operates and to implement innovative business models incorporating new digital tools and sustainability and circular economy concepts to shift to a resilient, competitive and resource efficient and carbon-neutral sector, able to face the challenges imposed by a globalized economy in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. Higher Education through knowledge transfer can make a significant contribution to helping SMEs overcome the current economic challenges.

REMODEL aims to strengthen R&I capacity and skills of Bursa Uludag University (BUU) through leveraging the experience and state-of-the-art knowledge and tools made available by twinning partners Universidad De Leon (ULE) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU). During the project, BUU will raise its research profile in innovative business models and significantly enhance its skills for the management and administration of EU R&I programmes, thanks to the training and networking programmes implemented in REMODEL. A novel Business Model Innovation (BMI) laboratory will be created and become instrumental for the execution of the Research part of the project by applying the acquired knowledge and skills in consumer behavioural analysis, neuromarketing, leadership and entrepreneurship gained by BUU to the development of innovative business models for 10 Turkish SMEs in the hospitality sector in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. A long-term scientific research strategy will be developed including joint academic studies, staff exchanges, and the definition of joint R&I programme.

With this motivation, the project will pursue five sub-objectives that are listed below:

- Raising the R&I profile of BUU in the development of innovative business models
- Raising the R&I capacity of BUU through staff exchanges, workshops, summer schools, and setting up of a BMI laboratory
- Strengthening of BUU EU projects and technology-transfer office
- Development of innovative business models for SMEs in the Turkey hospitality sector by leveraging the novel BUU BMI Lab created in REMODEL.
- Effectively disseminate and communicate project results and outcomes to engage the relevant stakeholders in the value chain: from authorities to citizens

2.2. Consortium

The REMODEL consortium consists of one coordinator and two leading institutions. The list of project participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: REMODEL Consortium

Role	Name	Acronym	Country	Contact Person	Contact Person's E-mail
COO	BURSA ULUDAG UNIVERSITY	BUU	Turkey	Aylin Poroy Arsoy	aporoy@uludag.edu.tr
BEN	UNIVERSIDAD DE LEON	ULE	Spain	Carmen R. Santos	carmen.santos@unileon.es
BEN	ATLANTIC TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	ATU	Ireland	Padraig Gallagher	padraig.gallagher@atu.ie

2.3. REMODEL Work Program

REMODEL work program has been divided in 3 inter-related activity areas as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: REMODEL Work Program

Area	Related Work Package (WP)	Key Activities
Area 1: BUU Capacity Building 1a. BUU R&I Performance and Management Capacity Building 1b. BUU BMI Lab Set Up	WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills and knowledge transfer of BUU academic and administrative staff • Creation of the BUU BMI lab
Area 2: Research Programme (SME Pilots)	WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research in innovative business models leveraging the BUU BMI lab applied to the hospitality sector in Turkey
Area 3: Long-term Impact Generation (Sustainability)	WP3-WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summer school organisation and staff exchanges. Preparation of a strategic-research agenda and long-term cooperation strategy • Liaison and clustering with policy makers, related projects and relevant institutions

Area 1: BUU Capacity Building: All the activities dedicated to increase the R&I capacity of BUU at scientific, management and administrative levels are grouped here, corresponding to WP2 “BUU research capacity building”. Recognised experts from ULE and ATU will provide training to BUU staff through workshops and lectures mainly focused on business, leadership, innovation, marketing, sustainability. Training will also include academic & scientific writing and R&I management and administration which mainly focused on enhancing the scientific capacity of BUU researchers. Area 1 also includes BMI laboratory workshops, leveraging from the existing Consumer Behaviour Analysis laboratory at ULE and the ATU DiceLab.

Area 2: Research Programme: A joint research programme will be carried out employing the novel BUU BMI laboratory. The scope will be the development of innovative business models for SMEs in the hospitality sector in Turkey. The activity is organized in WP4 “Research in innovative business models leveraging on the BMI Lab” and will be the means to apply the improved R&I performance and managing skills gained in WP2 to real case scenarios.

Area 3: Long-term Impact Generation: Continuity and sustainability of the cooperation consolidated within REMODEL is essential for the project partners. In that sense, a set of activities have been planned within WP3 “Twinning and networking” in order to guarantee the sustainability of the cooperation. A strategic research agenda (SRA) will be prepared including joint project proposals preparation, joint academic publications, clustering and networking, inventory relevant associations and platforms at EU level, list of conferences and congresses to attend, and joint academic programmes preparation. A series of workshops and summer schools will be organized to engage students and companies that can benefit from the R&I capacities and academic excellence offered by REMODEL partners.

2.4. Work Packages

The work plan of REMODEL is aligned with the concept and objectives of the project. It is organized into five work packages. REMODEL's overall Work Packages and their relations are presented in Figure 1. Detailed information about WPs are presented in Table 3.

Figure 1: REMODEL Overall WP Structure

Table 3: REMODEL Work Packages

WP Number and Name	Objective	Leading Institution	WP Leader
WP1- Project Management	The objectives of the WP1 are to ensure the effective administration of the project activities, to ensure that all project outcomes are of high quality, and to ensure that all potential risks are identified and appropriate mitigation actions are taken.	BUU	Yasemin ERTAN (BUU)
WP2- BUU Research Capacity Building ATU	The objectives of the WP2 are to efficient capacitation of BUU academic and R&I staff on consumer behavior analysis, innovative business modeling methodologies, research management, and administration, and creation of the BUU BMI Laboratory	ATU	Anne Burke (ATU) Conor McTiernan (ATU)
WP3- Twinning and Networking	The objectives of the WP3 are to define a common strategic research agenda among the twinning entities; organize summer schools, staff exchanges, and short visits and define long-term networking and R&I cooperation strategy among REMODEL Partners and key stakeholders.	ULE	Carmen R. Santos (ULE)
WP4- Research in Innovative Business Models Leveraging BMI Lab	The objectives of the WP4 are to analyze the Hospitality sector in Turkey and develop innovative business models for Turkish SMEs in the Hospitality Sector BUU	BUU	Nuran Bayram Arlı (BUU) Çağatan Taşkın (BUU)
WP5- Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, and Out Reach	The objectives of the WP5 are to efficiently disseminate and communicate REMODEL results, prepare for successful joint and individual exploitation and prepare R&I incentives policy recommendations to Turkish funding and policy-making agencies BUU	Elif Yücel (BUU)	Elif Yücel (BUU)

3. PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

This section of the Project Handbook contains information about the governance structure of the project, rules for maintaining effective internal and external communication, and conflict resolution.

3.1. Governance Structure, Roles, and Responsibilities

Project organization is an important project management activity. For the successful continuation and conclusion of the project, it is necessary to establish an effective governance structure and to determine roles and responsibilities for each level of governance structure.

The governance structure of the REMODEL (see Figure 2) is composed of Project Coordinator (PC), Project Management Board (PMB), General Assembly (GA), Executive Board (EB), Work Package Leaders (WPLs). The organization, coordination, and overall management of the Consortium will be led by the BUU through the PMB, supported by the EB. EB is the decision-making and monitoring body of REMODEL which will ensure the effective implementation of the activities and the achievement of the objectives of the project within the foreseen deadlines. It consists of all WP leaders. Roles and responsibilities for each level of governance structure are further described below.

Figure 2: Project Management Structure

Project Coordinator (PC)

Name:	Aylin POROY ARSOY
Organization:	BUU
Roles and Responsibilities:	<p>PC is an intermediary between the EU and Consortium. PC is responsible for: (in line with CA Article 6.4.2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under the CA and the Grant Agreement ● Keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available ● Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and other requested documents to the Granting Authority ● Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned ● Administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority ● Providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

The PMB of REMODEL consists of Project Manager, Financial Manager, Communication Manager, Data Manager, and Exploitation Manager. The managers support PC to fulfill above mentioned responsibilities.

Project Manager (PM)

Name:	Yasemin ERTAN
Organization:	BUU
Roles and Responsibilities:	PM supports PC for overall project management activities. PM ensures day-to-day communication with the consortium, assists in the preparation of periodic reports for the EC, and organizes meetings and training.

Financial Manager (FM)

Name:	Tuba BORA KILINÇARSLAN
Organization:	BUU
Roles and Responsibilities:	FM supports PC for all financial aspects of the project such as ensuring consistency between the project work plan and financial guidelines, ensuring the consortium payments are in accordance with budget consumption and supporting the preparation of periodic financial reports.

Communication Manager (CM)

Name:	Elif YÜCEL
Organization:	BUU
Roles and Responsibilities:	CM leads to creating a communication strategy and is responsible for efficiently disseminating and communicating REMODEL results. In this context, CM leads the creation of REMODEL visual identity, an easy-to-access website, and the REMODEL social media accounts continuously monitor the communication activities and support the preparation of periodic reports.

Data Manager (DM)

Name:	Burak MEYDANCI
Organization:	BUU
Roles and Responsibilities:	DM leads the preparation of the Data Management Plan (DMP) the Data Management Team. DM and the Data Management Team are responsible for ensuring the protection of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of the respective outputs including data management and support to the preparation of periodic reports.

Exploitation Manager (EM)

Name:	Padraig GALLAGHER
Organization:	ATU
Roles and Responsibilities:	EM is responsible for maximizing outcomes and long-term impacts of the project. EM leads to create a long-term networking and R&I cooperation strategy among REMODEL Partners and key stakeholders.

General Assembly (GA)

<p>Name and Organization:</p>	<p>Aylin Poroy ARSOY- BUU Padraig GALLAGHER- ATU Carmen R. SANTOS- ULE</p>
<p>Roles and Responsibilities:</p>	<p>The GA is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. The GA shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out by the CA. In addition, all proposals made by the Executive Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the GA. The following decisions shall be taken by the GA: (in line with CA Article 6.3.1.2)</p> <p>Content, Finances and IPR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority ● Changes to the Consortium Plan ● Modifications or withdrawal of CA Attachment Background Included ● Additions to CA Attachment List of Third Parties for simplified transfer ● Evolution of the consortium ● Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party ● Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal ● Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this CA or the Grant Agreement ● Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party ● Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party ● Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the Project and measures relating thereto ● Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the COO ● Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project ● Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the CA <p>On the basis of the Grant Agreement, the appointment if necessary of EB Members.</p>

Executive Board (EB)

<p>Name and Organization:</p>	<p>Aylin POROY ARSOY- PC Yasemin ERTAN- WP1 Leader Anne BURKE- WP2- Leader Conor MCTIERNAN- WP2- Leader Carmen R. SANTOS- WP3 Leader Nuran BAYRAM ARLI- WP4 Leader Çağatan TAŞKIN- WP4 Leader Elif YÜCEL- WP5 Leader</p>
<p>Roles and Responsibilities:</p>	<p>EB as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the GA. The EB shall consist of the Coordinator and the representatives of the Parties appointed to it by the GA.</p> <p>EB shall be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GA.</p> <p>EB shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project.</p> <p>In addition, EB shall collect information at least every six months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the GA. EB shall: (in line with CA Article 6.3.2.3.6)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables ● Prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section 8 of this CA

3.2. Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is vital for the success of the project. This section covers the points that need to be considered in order to communicate effectively within the consortium.

3.3.1. E-Mail

E-mails are one of the most used tools to communicate. Using a standard subject title will allow project-related e-mails to be quickly recognized and differentiated from other emails. Project-related e-mails should include in the subject title “REMODEL: WP Number (if applicable), followed by a more specific description of the subject, deadline for feedback or reply, etc.” For example:

“REMODEL: WP 1, Handbook revision, till January 15th”

For effective internal communication, it is necessary to copy the e-mail to all project personnel concerned to e-mail subject. If the subject of the e-mail is important for the execution and implementation of the project, the e-mail should be copied to the PC (aporoy@uludag.edu.tr) and the PM (yasertan@uludag.edu.tr).

Project personnel’s contact information can be found on SharePoint. If there is a change in the contact information, the PC should be notified of this change (aporoy@uludag.edu.tr).

3.2.2. Document Sharing and Storage

A cloud computing platform (Microsoft teams) has been created for REMODEL to facilitate proper communication and document sharing among project personnel. The cloud computing platform acts as a repository for project documents as well as a management tool to organize meetings and training.

Microsoft teams will be used as a SharePoint to share, collaboratively worked on, and store documents. All project staff have been added to the REMODEL team as members: All project-relevant documents will be placed there within a dedicated folder structure.

The address of the REMODEL teams file:

REMODEL Files

By using SharePoint, all project staff can read, download, edit and upload files. Also a teams calendar has been created to organize meetings, deadlines for deliverables, training, etc. By using Team Calendar, it will be possible to ensure the time management of the project.

3.2.3. Meetings

During the lifetime of REMODEL, GA and EB will convene ordinary and extraordinary meetings. In addition to these, project meetings will be held. And other informal meetings may also be held between some WP leaders or between WP leaders and WP team members. These meetings can be held face-to-face or online. Online meetings will be held through Microsoft teams. Doodle form will be used for providing consensus on scheduling meeting dates and times.

Summarized information about the meetings of REMODEL is presented in Table 4.

Before the meetings, the meeting agenda will be prepared and shared with the attendees within the time specified. During the meetings, an attendance list signed by attendees (face-to-face meetings) or marked by Chairperson (online/hybrid meetings) will be created. Certificates will be provided at the end of the meeting. Minutes of the meetings will be prepared and shared with the attendees.

Templates for each document are shared with staff via REMODEL teams file. All project documents should be prepared in accordance with the template prepared for them.

The methods and the months in which the meetings are planned to be held during the life of REMODEL are presented in Table 5, 6 & 7. If it is decided by the GA that it will be in favor of the project in terms of its implementation and/or in unexpected situations; and/or due to force majeure GA may make changes in the months when the meetings will be convened and their methods.

Table 4: REMODEL Meeting

Meeting	Type	Times During Project Life-Time	Notice of The Meeting (Minimum number of days Preceding The Meeting)	Sending The Agenda (Minimum Number of Days Preceding The Meeting)	Chairperson	Attendees	Adding Agenda Items	Minutes of Meetings
General Assembly	Ordinary Meeting	7 Times	30 Calendar Days	21 Calendar Days	Aylin Poroy Arsoy (PC)	GA Members and Ther Staff If Needed (Listening Only)	14 Calendar Days	Within 10 Calendar Days
General Assembly	Extraordinary Meeting	Any Time Upon Request of The EB or Any Member of The GA	15 Calendar Day	10 Calendar Days	Aylin Poroy Arsoy (PC)	GA Members and Ther Staff If Needed (Listening Only)	7 Calendar Days	Within 10 Calendar Days
Executive Board	Ordinary Meeting	13 Times	14 Calendar Days	7 Calendar Days	Aylin Poroy Arsoy (PC)	EB Members and Other Staff If Needed (listening only)	5 Calendar Days	Within 10 Calendar Days
Executive Board	Extraordinary Meeting	At Any Time Upon Request of Any Member of The EB	7 Calendar Days	5 Calendar Days	Aylin Poroy Arsoy (PC)	EB Members and Other Staff If Needed (listening only)	2 Calendar Days	Within 10 Calendar Days
Project Meeting	Ordinary Meeting	7 Times	30 Calendar Days	21 Calendar Days	Aylin Poroy Arsoy (PC)	All Project Researchers	14 Calendar Days	Within 10 Calendar Days
Other Informal Meetings	Extraordinary Meeting	At Any Time Upon Request of Any Member of The EB and GA	-	-	Any Member of the EB and GA	Needed Staff-Researchers(GA and EB Members)	-	Within 10 Calendar Days

Table 5: Time Schedule and Method of GA Meetings

Meeting	Month	Method
General Assembly-1	January 2023	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 2	July 2023	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 3	January 2024	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 4	June 2024	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 5	January 2025	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 6	June 2025	Face-to-face
General Assembly- 7	December 2025	Face-to-face

Table 6: Time Schedule and Method of EB Meetings

Meeting	Month	Method
Executive Board- 1	January 2023	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 2	April 2023	Online
Executive Board- 3	July 2023	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 4	October 2023	Online
Executive Board- 5	January 2024	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 6	April 2024	Online
Executive Board- 7	June 2024	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 8	October 2024	Online
Executive Board- 9	January 2025	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 10	April 2025	Online
Executive Board- 11	June 2025	Face-to-face
Executive Board- 12	October 2025	Online
Executive Board- 13	December 2025	Face-to-face

Table 7: Time Schedule and Method of Project Meetings

Meeting	Month	Method
Project Meeting- 1	January 2023	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 2	July 2023	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 3	January 2024	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 4	June 2024	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 5	January 2025	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 6	June 2025	Hybrid
Project Meeting- 7	December 2025	Hybrid

3.3. External Communication and Dissemination

In this section, general external communication rules are explained, and information is provided about the rules that should be followed when communicating with stakeholders and the EU project officers.

External communication is part of WP5 Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation. REMODEL communication strategy will be defined under D5.1. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (M06) providing specific Communication Guidelines with common actions and milestones implemented within the project span, ensuring the broadest impact on the targeted audience. However the REMODEL Branding and Visual Identity Guide has already been provided and shared with REMODEL WP leaders for ensuring the common visibility of the project.

3.3.1. Project Website and Social Media

The project website (domain: www.projectremodel.eu) will be set up and updated in line with the progress achieved in the project (M02). The project website acts as the main external communication and dissemination channel and includes general information about the project, events, deliverables, results, workshops, and training, and tailor-made materials (short videos, infographics, etc). Through the project website, all stakeholders will have the opportunity to have information about project activity and progress.

Multiple profiles have been created in different social media networks to enable project information to reach stakeholders. The social media accounts of the project are as follows:

- **Twitter:** https://twitter.com/project_remodel
- **Instagram:** https://www.instagram.com/remodel_project/?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y%3D
- **Linkedin:** <https://www.linkedin.com/in/remodel-project-933904259/>

Any content to be shared using social media should be sent to the WP 5 Leader Elif Yücel (emugal@uludag.edu.tr).

3.3.2. Acknowledgement

Any communication document (in any form, including public and confidential deliverables, conference/workshop presentations, and any type of information or promotional material) from the REMODEL project should include:

-The EU emblem and funding statement to highlight EU support and ensure the visibility of EU funding. The EU emblem must be given appropriate prominence when displayed together with the project's logo. and disclaimer text:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

The following statement is recommended to be included in all documents and communication channels to provide a wider identification of the project:

“This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101079203.”

In scientific publications, it is sufficient to have only the disclaimer text.

3.3.3. Logo

The REMODEL logo has been designed to reflect the fusion of business and innovation. The project logo and partners' logo must include all the project documents to raise project awareness. The project logo, partners' logo and the details to be considered when using logos is presented REMODEL Branding and Visual Identity Guide.

3.4. Document Preparation

Project documents are of vital importance for the execution and conclusions of the project and for the project to be understood by the stakeholders. Project documents are proof that project activities are carried out effectively. They are used to assess project progress by European Commission (EC). Some project documents are tools for internal communication and support project activities effectively. For example, through minutes of meetings, each project personnel can inform discussion points and decisions taken at the meeting even if they are not attending the meeting. Thus project personnel can perform their duties. Also, some documents give the opportunity for stakeholders to understand what activities are performed in the project and how the project procedures are handled. For example, public deliverables are important information resources for other projects. And finally, project documents are historical memories of the project. For all these reasons, project documents and their preparation are extremely important.

3.4.1. Document Templates

To obtain the expected benefit from project documents they should be prepared clearly, timely, and similarly. To ensure this, REMODEL document templates have been created for each type of project document and shared via teams file. The list of documents that should be prepared according to the related document templates are as follows:

- **Meeting Agendas:** It should be prepared before the meeting and should be shared with meeting participants.
- **Attendance Lists:** In face-to-face meetings and training, it should be signed by participants during the meeting. In online meetings and training, it should be marked by the Chairperson.
- **Certificates:** After face-to-face meetings and training, certificates should be given to the participants. After online meetings and training, certificates should be sent to the participants by e-mail.
- **Minutes of Meetings:** During the project's lifetime a lot of different kinds of meetings will be convened. After each type of meeting, minutes of the meeting will be prepared and shared with attendees.
- **Deliverables:** Totally Fifteen deliverables will be generated within the lifetime of REMODEL. All deliverables should be prepared in accordance with the deliverable templates.
- **Powerpoint Presentations:** Powerpoint template is created and shared with partners to be used in presentations about the project.

3.4.2. File Naming

In order to communicate effectively and avoid confusion, specific file naming formats should be used. The filename should contain the following items, respectively and items should be separated by an underscore (“_”):

- The Project name (REMODEL),
- The whole name of the document (e.g., D1.1. Project Handbook),
- The version letter “v” followed by the version number (two digits), for draft document first digits, is 0 and for final documents, first digit should be 1. The second digit refers to version numbers.

For example, the document for the first draft version of the project handbook should be named as follows:

“REMODEL_ D1.1 Project Handbook_ v01”.

All project documents should be uploaded to and stored in the REMODEL teams file.

3.5. Conflict Resolution

In multinational projects, such as REMODEL, conflicts may arise among the project personnel due to the cultural differences of the partners, differences in their working styles, and communication in a language other than their mother tongue. Conflicts that may occur within the project personnel are a type of risk and a management strategy should be developed to prevent, mitigate, and resolve this risk.

Creating an effective management structure and determining the roles and responsibilities of each level in this management structure is extremely important to prevent and mitigate conflicts.

However, conflicts may arise between different levels of the project management structure during the project. Developing a management strategy for conflict resolution is extremely important in terms of project coordination so that conflicts are resolved as soon as possible before they escalate. In the case of a conflict arising among project personnel, if possible the lowest decision-making body resolves the conflict amicably. If the conflict couldn't be resolved in the lowest decision-making body, a hierarchical conflict resolution process should be followed, as seen in Table 8.

Table 8: Conflict Resolution Process

Parties in Conflict	First Step	Second Step	Third Step	Forth Step
Between WP Team Members	WP Leader	Executive Board	General Assembly	Voting at the General Assembly
Between a WP Leader and WP Team Members	Executive Board	General Assembly	Voting at the General Assembly	
Between WP Leaders	Executive Board	General Assembly	Voting at the General Assembly	
Between Project Management Board Members	Project Coordinator	General Assembly	Voting at the General Assembly	
Between a PMB Member and WP Leader	Project Coordinator	General Assembly	Voting at the General Assembly	

As presented in Table 8, if there is a conflict between WP team members, firstly WP Leaders try to solve the conflict with consensus. If the problem cannot be resolved at this level, it goes to the next step; in order words, EB tries to resolve the conflict. If the EB cannot resolve the conflict, the GA attempts to solve the conflict with consensus. If the parties cannot come to an agreement as a result of all these steps, the GA determines a solution by voting. This process continues for the other parties in conflict as stated in Table 8.

4. DELIVERABLES

The Remodel consists of five WPs that will generate a total of fifteen deliverables presented in Table 9.

Table 9: List of Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Delivery Date (Month)
D1.1	Project Handbook	1	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M02
D1.2	Data Management Plan	1	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M6
D1.3	Quality & Risk Assessment Reports	1	BUU	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M12
D1.4	Progress Report	1	BUU	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M17
D2.1	Description and Operational Procedures of the BUU BMI Lab	2	ATU	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M17
D2.2	Report On Training Activities and Accomplishment	2	ULE	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M24
D2.3	Research Management and Administration manual and Operational Procedures	2	BUU	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M24

Deliverable No	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Delivery Date (Month)
D3.1	Strategic Research Agenda for REMODEL Partnership	3	ULE	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M17
D3.2	Report on Staff Exchanges and Summer Schools	3	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M33
D4.1	Analysis of The Hospitality Sector in Turkey	4	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M15
D4.2	Optimised Methodologies to Develop Innovative Business Models for SMEs	4	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M36
D4.3	Report On Innovative R&I in BMI and Impact Assessment	4	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M36
D5.1	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan	5	BUU	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M6
D5.2	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Liaison, and Clustering Report	5	ULE	R — Document, Report	PU-Public	M36
D5.3	Policy Recommendations Brief	5	BUU	R — Document, Report	SEN - Sensitive	M36

Public - fully open (automatically posted online) Sensitive - limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

4.1. Deliverable Generation

WP Leaders are responsible for producing deliverables that are related to their WP with the support of WP Team Members. To assure the quality of the deliverables, the following points should be observed:

- Deliverables should be prepared in accordance with the deliverable template that is shared with project staff via REMODEL teams file.
- WP Leader should adhere to the deliverable generation schedule in Table 10.

Table 10: Deliverable Generation Schedule

30 Days Before Submission	WP leader and team members complete the draft deliverable; WP Leader sends to EB and PM for feedback and quality assurance
20 Days Before Submission	EB members and PM review the deliverable, provides feedback to the WP leader
15 Days Before Submission	WP Leader revises the deliverable considering EB's and PM's feedback and sends to GA for final feedback
10 Days Before Submission	GA members review the deliverable, provides feedback to the WP leader
5 Days Before Submission	The WP Leader sends final version of deliverable to the PC and the PM for final review. If needed PC and PM communicate with WP Leader.
2 Days Before Submission	The PC uploads the deliverable to the Portal Continuous Reporting tool

According to Table 10 Deliverable generation schedule, the time schedule of REMODEL deliverables is presented in Table 11.

Table 11 Time Schedule of REMODEL Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Draft Deliverable Deadline	EB-PM Feedback Deadline	Sending to GA for Final Feedback	GA Feedback Deadline	Sending to PC and PM For Final Review	Finalization and Uploading to PCR
D1.1	Project Handbook	January 27th, 2023	February 7th, 2023	February 12th, 2023	February 17th, 2023	February 22nd, 2023	February 27th, 2023
D1.2	Data Management Plan	May 28th, 2023	June 8th, 2023	June 13rd, 2023	June 18th, 2023	June 23rd, 2023	June 28th, 2023
D1.3	Quality & Risk Assessment Reports	November 29th, 2023	December 9th, 2023	December 14th, 2023	December 19th, 2023	December 24th, 2023	December 29th, 2023
D1.4	Progress Report	April 29th, 2024	May 9th, 2024	May 14th, 2024	May 19th, 2024	May 24th, 2024	May 29th, 2024
D2.1	Description and Operational Procedures of The BUJ BMI Lab	April 29th, 2024	May 9th, 2024	May 14th, 2024	May 19th, 2024	May 24th, 2024	May 29th, 2024
D2.2	Report on Training Activities and Accomplishment	November 29th, 2024	December 9th, 2024	December 14th, 2024	December 19th, 2024	December 24th, 2024	December 29th, 2024
D2.3	Research Management and Administration Manual and Operational Procedures	November 29th, 2024	December 9th, 2024	December 14th, 2024	December 19th, 2024	December 24th, 2024	December 29th, 2024
D3.1	Strategic Research Agenda for REMODEL Partnership	April 29th, 2024	May 9th, 2024	May 14th, 2024	May 19th, 2024	May 24th, 2024	May 29th, 2024
D3.2	Report on Staff Exchanges and Summer Schools	August 28th, 2025	September 8th, 2025	September 13rd, 2025	September 18th, 2025	September 23rd, 2025	September 28th, 2025
D4.1	Analysis of The Hospitality Sector in Turkey	February 29th, 2024	March 9th, 2024	March 14th, 2024	March 19th, 2024	March 24th, 2024	March 29th, 2024
D4.2	Optimised Methodologies to Develop Innovative Business Models for SMEs	November 29th, 2025	December 9th, 2025	December 14th, 2025	December 19th, 2025	December 24th, 2025	December 29th, 2025
D4.3	Report on Innovative R&I in BMI and Impact Assessment	November 29th, 2025	December 9th, 2025	December 14th, 2025	December 19th, 2025	December 24th, 2025	December 29th, 2025
D5.1	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan	May 28th, 2023	June 8th, 2023	June 13rd, 2023	June 18th, 2023	June 23rd, 2023	June 28th, 2023
D5.2	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Liaison, and Clustering Report	November 29th, 2025	December 9th, 2025	December 14th, 2025	December 19th, 2025	December 24th, 2025	December 29th, 2025
D5.3	Policy Recommendations Brief	November 29th, 2025	December 9th, 2025	December 14th, 2025	December 19th, 2025	December 24th, 2025	December 29th, 2025

The dates given in Table 11 are approximate dates +/- maximum two days are acceptable except from the “finalization and uploading to CRM” stage.

4.2. Identifying the Deliverables

During the deliverable generation process, the draft version of the document is exchanged among project staff many times as seen in Table 10. While finalizing the deliverable, it will be revised in line with the changes and developments that may occur during the generation process. Using specific file names format is extremely important to avoid confusion.

(See Project Handbook 3.4.2. For File Naming)

4.3. Quality Assurance of Deliverables

As stated in Section 4.1 Deliverables will be reviewed by the PM for assuring their quality. Reviewers should take into account the criteria in Table 12 throughout the reviewing process.

Table 12: Assurance Criteria

Criteria	EB	GA	PC	PM
Is the deliverable prepared according to the deliverable template?				X
Is the deliverable written in gender-sensitive language?	X	X	X	
Is the deliverable understandable?	X	X	X	
Has the ethical screening been performed?	X	X	X	
Is the purpose of the document clearly and accurately stated?	X	X	X	
Is the content in compliance with DoA?		X	X	X
Does the deliverable contain all the necessary information?	X	X	X	
Does the deliverable avoid unnecessary duplication?	X	X	X	

5. MILESTONES

Six milestones will be achieved during the lifetime of REMODEL. GA is responsible for monitoring these achievements timely. These milestones, their WP numbers, leads, and means of verification is presented in Table 13.

Table 13: List of Milestones

Milestone Number	Milestone Name	Related WP	Lead	Means of Verification	Due Date (Month)
MS1	KOM Held	WP1	BUU	Meeting Minutes	M1
MS2	BMI Lab Fully Operative	WP2	ATU	D2.1 Description and Operational Procedures of The BUU BMI Lab	M24
MS3	First SRA Draft Agreed	WP3	ULE	Meeting Minutes, D3.1 Strategic Research Agenda for REMODEL Partnership	M12
MS4	Summer Schools Successfully Held	WP3	BUU	D3.2 Report on Staff Exchanges and Summer Schools	M33
MS5	BMI Lab Methodology Optimised	WP4	BUU	D4.2 Optimised Methodologies to Develop Innovative Business Models for SMEs	M24
MS6	Successful DCE Strategy Implemented	WP5	ULE	Achievement of KPI	M36

Table 14: Overview for 2023

	Jan 23	Feb 23	Mar 23	Apr 23	May 23	Jun 23	Jul 23	Aug 23	Sep 23	Oct 23	Nov 23	Dec 23
WP1	MS1	D1.1				D1.2						D1.3
WP3												MS3
WP5						D5.1						

Table 15: Overview for 2024

	Jan 24	Feb 24	Mar 24	Apr 24	May 24	Jun 24	Jul 24	Aug 24	Sep 24	Oct 24	Nov 24	Dec 24
WP1					D1.4							
WP2					D2.1							D2.2 D2.3 MS2
WP3					D3.1							
WP4			D4.1									MS5

Table 16: Overview for 2025

	Jan 25	Feb 25	Mar 25	Apr 25	May 25	Jun 25	Jul 25	Aug 25	Sep 25	Oct 25	Nov 25	Dec 25
WP3									D3.2 MS4			
WP4												D4.2 D4.3
WP5												D5.2 D5.3 MS6

6. REPORTING

REMODEL deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, publications, dissemination and communication activities, datasets and impact will be reported and updated at any moment during the project; in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out via Portal Continuous Reporting tool in line with the Grant Agreement Article 21.1.

GA Members (including PC) and PM will be responsible for preparing and ensuring the accuracy of the reporting process. PC will submit the reports.

During the lifetime of REMODEL two reports will be submitted to the EC through the Portal Continuous Reporting tool: Periodic Report (M18) and Final report (M36).

The Periodic Report/ Financial Report is divided into a technical and financial report.

Technical Report		Financial Report
Part A	Part B	
Structured Tables with Project Information	Narrative Description of The Work Carried Out During The Reporting Period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The individual financial statements for each Beneficiary • A summary financial statement • A certificate on the financial statements (CFS) (if threshold reached).
Generated by the Portal Continuous Reporting Tool	PDF File (template is provided by EU)	

7. DATA MANAGEMENT

The first version of the DMP will be submitted as deliverable D2.2 (M6). The plan will be updated regularly.

In REMODEL, the research data and output generated in the project will be managed responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and Grant agreement Article 17:

- The initial DMP will be composed in M6, explaining in detail how the data generated in the project will be collected, processed and shared and made accessible by project partners. The IPR policy (i.e., IP, confidentiality and publication provisions) will be considered as defined in the CA. The DMP will be updated timely with changes in the consortium policies. A final DMP will be submitted in M36.
- The data will be deposited in a trusted repository within the deadlines set out in the DMP. All public deliverables and publications will be uploaded to Zenodo (Open access repository) which allows to assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to any type of project outcome.
- The deposited data will be made Open Access (OA) via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent license.
- Any information about research outputs and any other tools or instruments needed to reuse and/or validate data will be provided information via the repository.

REMODEL will also collect, manage and generate data on the different scientific activities. Datasets will be managed in line with the FAIR principles:

- **Findability:** For the data that can be made publicly available, a trusted OA repository will be used and a unique DOI to each dataset will be assigned. A naming convention and standard identification mechanism of the datasets for persistent identifiers will be decided among the project consortium partners in a later stage of the project.
- **Accessibility:** Data that do not interfere with commercial and industrial interests will be made OA through open access publications and the research data associated with such publications.
- **Interoperability:** When accessible, datasets should be readable, and able to be processed with ordinary computer software. Concerning data generation from experimental activities, the data format should assure interoperability.
- **Reusability:** The datasets will be reusable if they are findable, accessible and interoperable in the long term.

A team responsible for data management is appointed at the beginning of the project (Table 17):

Table 17: The Data Management Team

Name	Institution	E mail	Role
Burak Meydancı	BUU	bmeydanci@uludag.edu.tr	REMODEL Data Manager
Juanita Blue	ATU	juanita.Blue@atu.ie	REMODEL Data Management Team Member
Sofía Blanco Moreno	ULE	sblanm@unileon.es	REMODEL Data Management Team member

Data Management Team will be responsible to make sure that the REMODEL data management plan (DMP) is developed, implemented, and maintained which will outline the data generated, the plans for sharing them, copyright and IPR issues, data storage, and report the data that is shared. DMP will continuously monitor the data management process during the lifetime of the Project.

8. BUDGET MANAGEMENT AND REPORTING

Estimated budget for REMODEL and the distribution of the budget among categories per institution, distribution of budget by category, distribution of budget by partners are presented in Table 18 and following graphics.

Table 18: REMODEL Estimated Budget

	Personnel Costs	Purchase Costs			Indirect Costs	Total	Maximum EU Contribution
		Travel and Subsistence	Equipment	Other Goods, Works and Services			
BUU	380,000	56,700	6,000	57,600	57,600	625,375	625,375
ULE	216,062	34,200	0	37,300	71,890.5	359,452.5	359,452.5
ATU	315,000	36,000	0	61,000	103,000	515,000	515,000

BUU

■ Personnel Costs

■ Indirect Costs

■ Other Goods, Works and Services

■ Purchase Costs Travel and Subsistence

■ Equipment

Figure 3: BUU Budget Allocation

ULE

- Personnel Costs
- Indirect Costs
- Other Goods, Works and Services
- Purchase Costs Travel and Subsistence

Figure 4: ULE Budget Allocation

ATU

- Personnel Costs
- Indirect Costs
- Other Goods, Works and Services
- Purchase Costs Travel and Subsistence

Figure 5: ATU Budget Allocation

■ Personnel Costs

■ Indirect Costs

■ Other Goods, Works and Services

■ Purchase Costs Travel and Subsistence

■ Equipment

Figure 6: REMODEL Budget Allocation by Category

■ BUU

■ ULE

■ ATU

Figure 7: REMODEL Budget Allocation by Partners

Table 19: REMODEL Budget Categories And Forms of Funding

Budget Category	Form of Funding
Direct Costs:	
Personnel Costs:	Actual Costs
Purchase Costs; Travel And Subsistence	Actual Costs
Purchase Costs; Equipment	Actual Costs
Purchase Costs; Other Goods, Works and Services	Actual Costs
Indirect Costs:	Flat Rate Costs (flat-rate: 25% of the eligible direct costs)

For general eligibility conditions please refer to Grant Agreement Article 6.1

For specific eligibility conditions for each budget category please refer to Grant Agreement Article 6.2

For ineligible costs and contributions please refer to Grant Agreement Article 6.3

For record keeping requirements please refer to Grant Agreement Article 20